

POLICY AND INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT FOR EQUITABLE ASSESSMENT AND CULTURALLY RELEVANT PEDAGOGY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Syed Rahat Ali¹, Muhammad Shoaib^{*2}, Shamraiz Iqbal³, Farooq Abdullah⁴

¹M. Phil Student, Department of Sociology, University of Gujrat, Gujrat, Pakistan

²Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, University of Gujrat, Gujrat, Pakistan

³PhD Scholar, Department of Gender Studies, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴Lecturer, Department of Sociology, Mirpur University of Science & Technology, Mirpur, AJ&K, Pakistan

¹rahatasoc@gmail.com, ²shoaibsoc@uog.edu.pk, ³shamraiznatt@gmail.com, ⁴farooq.abdullah@must.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18106101>

Keywords

Institutional Support, Equitable Assessment, Culture, Pedagogy, Students

Article History

Received: 11 October 2025

Accepted: 21 November 2025

Published: 31 December 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Shoaib

Abstract

The main aim of this study was to examine policy and institutional support for equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy among university students. A quantitative research design was employed, focusing on BS (4-year) students from a public sector university in Punjab, Pakistan. Using proportionate random sampling, 316 students were selected, with sample sizes proportionally allocated to each department within the Faculty of Social Sciences. Data were collected through a structured, cross-sectional questionnaire covering socio-economic background, gender disparity in enrolment, classroom participation, and learning environment. The tool was pretested with 30 students, using a Likert-type scale, and reliability was confirmed with Cronbach's Alpha above 0.700. As the data were non-parametric, analysis was conducted using frequency distributions and descriptive discussion. The study concludes that institutional policies and support are key determinants in promoting equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy. Equitable assessment allows all students, irrespective of cultural, linguistic, or socio-economic backgrounds, to fairly demonstrate learning, while culturally relevant pedagogy enhances engagement, inclusion, and belonging. Findings highlight the importance of clear policy guidelines, faculty resources, and professional development for effective implementation. Strengthened institutional support is essential for fostering inclusive learning environments and equitable academic opportunities in higher education.

INTRODUCTION

Equity and inclusiveness have become central concerns in contemporary higher education, particularly in relation to assessment practices and pedagogical approaches that serve increasingly diverse student populations (Kamenou, 2020; Shoaib, 2021; Shoaib & Ullah, 2019; Abdullah &

Nisar, 2024). Universities today enroll students from varied cultural, linguistic, socio-economic, and educational backgrounds, making it essential for teaching and assessment systems to be fair, responsive, and supportive of all learners (CohenMiller et al., 2022; Shoaib, Abdullah, et

al., 2021; Shoaib, Ali, et al., 2021; Abdullah & Ullah, 2016). In this context, policy frameworks and institutional support play a crucial role in shaping how equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy are understood, implemented, and sustained within university settings (Davies et al., 2024; Shoaib & Ullah, 2021a, 2021b; Abdullah & Ullah, 2022). Assessment is a powerful component of the teaching learning process, as it influences students' motivation, learning strategies, and academic outcomes (Rao & Sweetman, 2014; Shoaib, 2023a, 2023b; Abdullah, Matloob, & Malik, 2024). Inequitable assessment practices such as rigid evaluation methods, cultural bias, or limited opportunities for feedback disadvantage certain groups of students and perpetuate systemic inequalities (Henderson & Herring, 2013; Shoaib, 2024a, 2024c). Equitable assessment, on the other hand, emphasizes fairness, transparency, flexibility, and alignment with diverse learners' needs, enabling students to demonstrate their learning in meaningful and accessible ways (Herzig, 2010; Shoaib, 2024b, 2024d).

Culturally relevant pedagogy further complements equitable assessment by recognizing and valuing students' cultural identities, experiences, and ways of knowing as assets in the learning process (Shoaib, 2024e; Shoaib, Ali, et al., 2024; Abdullah et al., 2024). By connecting academic content to students' lived experiences and cultural contexts, culturally relevant teaching promotes engagement, academic confidence, and a sense of belonging (Shoaib, Shehzadi, et al., 2024a, 2024b; Abdullah, Nisar, & Malik, 2024). However, the effective adoption of such pedagogy often depends on the extent to which institutions provide supportive policies, professional development, and resources for faculty. Policy and institutional support serve as foundational mechanisms for promoting equitable educational practices in universities (Ahmed et al., 2025; Shoaib, Zaman, et al., 2024; Abdullah, Nisar, & Ahmed, 2025). Institutional policies related to curriculum design, assessment standards, faculty training, and student support services either enable or constrain the implementation of equity-oriented approaches (Ali et al., 2025; Shoaib, 2025b). Without clear

policy guidance and sustained institutional commitment, efforts to adopt equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy remain fragmented or inconsistent (Shoaib, 2025a; Shoaib, Ahmed, & Iqbal, 2025; Abdullah, Sultana, & Nisar, 2025).

Against this backdrop, the present study, "policy and institutional support for equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy among university students," seeks to examine how university policies and institutional structures support or hinder the adoption of equitable assessment practices and culturally relevant teaching. By exploring these dimensions, the study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of how higher education institutions foster inclusive learning environments that promote fairness, academic success, and meaningful learning experiences for all university students.

Study Context

Universities are increasingly enrolling diverse student populations, encompassing a wide range of cultural, linguistic, socio-economic, and educational backgrounds (Shoaib, Ahmed, Iqbal, et al., 2025; Shoaib, Ahmed, & Usmani, 2025a; Abdullah, Shoukat, Malik, Akhtar, 2025). This diversity presents both opportunities and challenges for higher education institutions, particularly in ensuring that teaching, learning, and assessment practices are equitable and inclusive (Shoaib, Ahmed, & Usmani, 2025b; Shoaib, Ahmed, Zaman, et al., 2025). However, universities often have formal policies and guidelines intended to support fair and culturally responsive education, the actual experiences of students vary significantly depending on how these policies are implemented and supported at the institutional level (Shoaib, Ali, Iqbal, et al., 2025; Shoaib, Ali, & Noreena Kausar, 2025; Abdullah, Sultana, Nisar, & Gorski, 2025). Assessment practices in many universities have traditionally been standardized and often emphasize uniform metrics of performance (Shoaib & Bashir, 2025; Shoaib, Batool, et al., 2025). Such approaches inadvertently disadvantage students from non-dominant cultural or linguistic backgrounds, whose ways of

thinking, expressing knowledge, or engaging in academic tasks differ from mainstream expectations (Shoaib, Iqbal, et al., 2025; Shoaib, Iqbal, et al., 2025; Abdullah, Sultana, & Nisar, 2025). Equitable assessment practices such as diversified evaluation methods, inclusive grading rubrics, and flexible opportunities for demonstrating learning aim to mitigate these disparities and provide all students with fair opportunities to succeed (Shoaib, Kausar, et al., 2025; Shoaib, Rasool, & Iqbal, 2025c).

Culturally relevant pedagogy emphasizes the integration of students' cultural experiences, knowledge, and perspectives into teaching and learning processes (Shoaib, Rasool, & Iqbal, 2025a, 2025b). By valuing and leveraging the diverse backgrounds of students, educators enhance engagement, motivation, and a sense of belonging within the academic environment (Shoaib, Rasool, Iqbal, et al., 2025a, 2025b; Abdullah, Nisar, Ahmed, & Sultana, 2025). However, the successful implementation of culturally relevant pedagogy often relies on institutional support, including faculty development programs, curriculum frameworks, and resources that guide inclusive teaching practices (Shoaib, Rasool, Kalsoom, et al., 2025; Shoaib, Rasool, & Zaman, 2025b). Institutional policies play a crucial role in shaping both assessment and pedagogy (Shoaib, Rasool, & Zaman, 2025a, 2025c). Clear guidelines, professional development initiatives, and supportive administrative structures empower faculty to adopt equity-oriented practices consistently (Shoaib, Rasool, Zaman, & Abdullah, 2025; Shoaib, Rasool, Zaman, & Ahmed, 2025). Conversely, gaps in policy enforcement, limited resources, or lack of institutional prioritization hinder efforts to create inclusive and culturally responsive learning environments (Shoaib, Shamsheer, et al., 2025; Shoaib et al., 2025). In this context, the present study investigates how university policies and institutional support influence the implementation of equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy. By examining these factors, the study seeks to understand the extent to which institutional frameworks facilitate or constrain inclusive

teaching and learning practices, ultimately affecting students' academic engagement, achievement, and overall educational experiences. Hence, the main aim of the study is to examine policy and institutional support for equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy among university students.

The Data and Methods

This research paper has been based on quantitative study design having sample size more than 30. It has been conducted in one public sector university in the Punjab province. The students of BS 4 years constitute the population of the study. The sampling frame has been collected and a sample of 316 students have been selected using proportionate random sampling technique. The sample size has been proportionally allocated to each department of the faculty of the social sciences of the university. A cross-sectional survey has been conducted and structured questionnaire has been developed to collect quality data. The measurement tool has been consisted of sections including socio-economic (separate questions), gender disparity in enrolment (matrix questions), gender disparity in classroom (matrix questions), and gender disparity in learning environment (matrix questions). This tool has been pretested from 30 randomly selected students and an altitudinal scale of agreement and disagreement has been used. The reliability test has been confirmed by the value of Alpha (above .700). The data has been found non-parametric. Hence, frequency distribution and discussion has been done to present the data.

Results

Equitable Assessment Methods:

Table 1 provided the response of the student's reference to equitable assessment methods. The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement "your assessment has been based on transparently". The analysis based on field data pointed out that 10.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 25.0 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement "your assessment has been based on transparently".

Similarly, the analysis revealed that 11.0 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 53.9 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your assessment has been based on transparently”.

Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your assessment has been based on transparently”.

Table 1 Response of the Students towards Equitable Assessment Methods
SA=Strongly Agree to D=Disagree

S. No.	Statement	SD f(%)	D f(%)	A f(%)	SA f(%)
i	Your assessment has been based on transparently	31 (10.1)	77 (25.0)	166 (53.9)	34 (11.0)
ii	Multiple assessment <u>method</u> has been used in your class	15 (4.9)	81 (26.3)	178 (57.8)	34 (11.0)
iii	Teachers use <u>standardize</u> assessment methods	27 (8.8)	74 (24.0)	156 (50.6)	51 (16.6)
iv	Your evaluation has been based on merit	25 (8.1)	70 (22.7)	159 (51.6)	54 (17.5)
v	Your assessment has been done on time	20 (6.5)	70 (22.7)	172 (55.8)	46 (14.9)
vi	Your assessment has been accessed by sessional work	25 (8.1)	71 (23.1)	157 (51.0)	55 (17.9)
vii	Your assessment has been based on presentation skills	26 (8.4)	62 (20.1)	153 (49.7)	67 (21.8)
viii	Your assessment is based on exams in the semester	30 (9.7)	52 (16.9)	154 (50.0)	72 (23.4)

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “multiple assessment method has been used in your class”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 4.9 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 26.3 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “multiple assessment method has been used in your class”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 11.0 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 57.8 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “multiple assessment method has been used in your class”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “multiple assessment method has been used in your class”. The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “teachers use standardize assessment methods”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 8.8 percent of the male and female students were

strongly disagree and 24.0 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “teachers use standardize assessment methods”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 16.6 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 50.6 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “teachers use standardize assessment methods”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “teachers use standardize assessment methods”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your evaluation has been based on merit”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 8.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 22.7 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your evaluation has been based on merit”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 17.5 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 51.6 percent of the students were agree with the items as

mentioned in table “your evaluation has been based on merit”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your evaluation has been based on merit”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your assessment has been done on time”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 6.5 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 22.7 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your assessment has been done on time”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 14.9 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 55.8 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your assessment has been done on time”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your assessment has been done on time”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your assessment has been accessed by sessional work”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 8.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 23.1 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your assessment has been accessed by sessional work”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 17.9 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 51.0 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your assessment has been accessed by sessional work”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your assessment has been accessed by sessional work”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your assessment has been based on presentation skills”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 8.4 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 20.1 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your assessment has been based on presentation skills”.

Similarly, the analysis revealed that 21.8 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 49.7 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your assessment has been based on presentation skills”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your assessment has been based on presentation skills”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your assessment is based on exams in the semester”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 9.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 16.9 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your assessment is based on exams in the semester”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 23.4 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 50.0 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your assessment is based on exams in the semester”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your assessment is based on exams in the semester”.

Policy and Institutional Support:

Table 2 provided the response of the student’s reference to policy and institutional support. The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “you practice standardize rules in the university”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 9.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 26.0 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “you practice standardize rules in the university”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 12.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 51.6 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “you practice standardize rules in the university”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “you practice standardize rules in the university”.

Table 2 Response of the Students towards policy and institutional support
SA=Strongly Agree to D=Disagree

S. No.	Statement	SD f(%)	D f(%)	A f(%)	SA f(%)
i	You practice standardize rules in the university	30 (9.7)	80 (26.0)	159 (51.6)	39 (12.7)
ii	Physical facilities have been provided to you	32 (10.4)	88 (28.6)	146 (47.4)	42 (13.6)
iii	Software have been provided to you in the university	35 (11.4)	82 (26.6)	149 (48.4)	42 (13.6)
iv	Transport facilities have been provided to you	33 (10.7)	69 (22.4)	141 (45.8)	65 (21.1)
v	University resources have been equally distributed	35 (11.4)	109 (35.4)	126 (40.9)	38 (12.3)
vi	You have full institutional support for your study	29 (9.4)	101 (32.8)	145 (47.1)	33 (10.7)
vii	University implement different policies as per routine	25 (8.1)	81 (26.3)	163 (52.9)	39 (12.7)
viii	Your university focus on smooth educational activities	30 (9.7)	96 (31.2)	137 (44.5)	45 (14.6)

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “physical facilities have been provided to you”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 10.4 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 28.6 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “physical facilities have been provided to you”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 13.6 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 47.4 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “physical facilities have been provided to you”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “physical facilities have been provided to you”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “software has been provided to you in the university”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 11.4 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 26.6 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “software have been provided to you in the university”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 13.6 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 48.4 percent of the

students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “software have been provided to you in the university”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “software has been provided to you in the university”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “transport facilities have been provided to you”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 10.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 22.4 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “transport facilities have been provided to you”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 21.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 45.8 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “transport facilities have been provided to you”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “transport facilities have been provided to you”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “university resources have been equally distributed”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 11.4 percent of the male and

female students were strongly disagree and 35.4 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “university resources have been equally distributed”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 12.3 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 40.9 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “university resources have been equally distributed”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “university resources have been equally distributed”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “you have full institutional support for your study”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 9.4 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 32.8 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “you have full institutional support for your study”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 10.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 47.1 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “you have full institutional support for your study”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “you have full institutional support for your study”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “university implement different policies as per routine”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 8.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 26.3 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “university implement different policies as per routine”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 12.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 52.9 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “university implement different policies as per routine”. Hence, it concluded that most of the

male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “university implement different policies as per routine”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your university focus on smooth educational activities”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 9.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 31.2 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your university focus on smooth educational activities”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 14.6 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 44.5 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your university focus on smooth educational activities”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your university focus on smooth educational activities”.

Culturally Relevant Teaching Materials:

Table 3 provided the response of the student’s reference to culturally relevant teaching materials. The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “your study material has been based on cultural codes”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 11.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 33.1 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “your study material has been based on cultural codes”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 12.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 42.5 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “your study material has been based on cultural codes”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “your study material has been based on cultural codes”.

Table 3 Response of the Students towards Culturally Relevant Teaching Materials

SA=Strongly Agree to D=Disagree

S. No.	Statement	SD <i>f</i> (%)	D <i>f</i> (%)	A <i>f</i> (%)	SA <i>f</i> (%)
i	Your study material has been based on cultural codes	36	102	131	39

		(11.7)	(33.1)	(42.5)	(12.7)
ii	Cultural values has been practiced in classroom	28	95	149	36
		(9.1)	(30.8)	(48.4)	(11.7)
iii	Dress code has been implemented	28	117	131	32
		(9.1)	(38.0)	(42.5)	(10.4)
iv	Cultural values are very important in the classroom	31	87	145	45
		(10.1)	(28.2)	(47.1)	(14.6)
v	Gender based study culture has been practiced	25	106	143	34
		(8.1)	(34.4)	(46.4)	(11.0)
vi	Students have freedom to practice cultural values	15	69	174	50
		(4.9)	(22.4)	(56.5)	(16.2)
vii	Students respects the teachers	17	54	159	78
		(5.5)	(17.5)	(51.6)	(25.3)
viii	Each student has respect in classroom in front of others	22	59	154	73
		(7.1)	(19.2)	(50.0)	(23.7)

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “cultural values has been practiced in classroom”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 9.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 30.8 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “cultural values has been practiced in classroom”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 11.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 48.4 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “cultural values has been practiced in classroom”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “cultural values has been practiced in classroom”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “dress code has been implemented”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 9.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 38.0 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “dress code has been implemented”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 10.4 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 42.5 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “dress code has been implemented”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “dress code has been implemented”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “cultural values are very important in the classroom”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 10.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 28.2 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “cultural values are very important in the classroom”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 14.6 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 47.1 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “cultural values are very important in the classroom”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “cultural values are very important in the classroom”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “gender based study culture has been practiced”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 8.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 34.4 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “gender based study culture has been practiced”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 11.0 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 46.4 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “gender based study culture has been practiced”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor

of the argument to the items in the tables “gender based study culture has been practiced”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “students have freedom to practice cultural values”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 4.9 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 22.4 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “students have freedom to practice cultural values”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 16.2 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 56.5 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “students have freedom to practice cultural values”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “students have freedom to practice cultural values”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “students respects the teachers”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 5.5 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 17.5 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “students respects the teachers”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 25.3 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 51.6 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “students respects the teachers”. Hence, it concluded that most of the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “students respect the teachers”.

The analysis asserted the percentages and response based on frequency against the statement “each student has respect in classroom in front of others”. The analysis based on field data pointed out that 7.1 percent of the male and female students were strongly disagree and 19.2 percent of the students disagree reference to the statement “each student has respect in classroom in front of others”. Similarly, the analysis revealed that 23.7 percent of the male and female students were strongly agree and only 50.0 percent of the students were agree with the items as mentioned in table “each student has respect in classroom in front of others”. Hence, it concluded that most of

the male and female students were in favor of the argument to the items in the tables “each student has respect in classroom in front of others”.

Discussion

Equitable Assessment Methods:

The study findings summarized that assessment of the students has been based on transparently. Similarly, the primary data analysis highlighted that multiple assessment method has been used in classroom of the students. Likewise, the study findings claimed that teachers use standardize assessment methods for students. However, the summary of the frequency distribution declared that student’s evaluation has been based on merit. Comparably, the statistical analysis confirmed that assessment of students has been done on time. Furthermore, the primary that analysis pointed out that assessment of students has been accessed by sessional work. Correspondingly, the study findings asserted that assessment of students has been based on presentation skills. In addition, the study findings indicated that student’s assessment is based on exams in the semester. The study findings had been linked with the study findings as mentioned in review. The study findings outline that talented female students motivation was impacted by unequal recognition of their achievements at higher education United States (Flores, 2017). In the same way, analysis of the study pointed out that student involvement and classroom inclusion were impacted by teachers use of gendered terminology in Australia (Ford, 2013). However, the results of the study articulated that disparity in opportunities effects to female students were discouraged from succeeding in technical education programs by unequal career options (Gallagher & Wahler, 2018). As the analysis of the research reported that girls access to co-educational learning environments might occasionally be restricted by religious traditions (Garcia et al., 2023). Furthermore, the study findings indicates that boys are often given preference over girls in apprenticeships and internships due to gender inequality in opportunities (Geduld, 2024; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025c; Shoaib & Zaman, 2025; Shoaib, Zaman, et al., 2025).

Policy and Institutional Support:

The study findings summarized that students practice standardize rules in the university. Similarly, the primary data analysis highlighted that student's physical facilities have been provided to you. Likewise, the study findings claimed that software have been provided to male and female students in the university. However, the summary of the frequency distribution declared that students transport facilities have been provided to you. Comparably, the statistical analysis confirmed that university resources of students have been equally distributed. Furthermore, the primary that analysis pointed out that institutional support for male and female students to study. Correspondingly, the study findings asserted that university implement different policies as per routine on students. In addition, the study findings indicated that university focus on smooth educational activities of the students. The study findings had been linked with the study findings as mentioned in review. The study findings outline that disparity is impactful for policy development is diminished by a lack of research on gender equity in education (Gehlert et al., 2010). In the same way, analysis of the study pointed out that families of developing countries spend less money on individual education for girls than for boys (Gentrup & Rjosk, 2018; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025b; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025b). However, the results of the study articulated that disparate allocation of educational resources significantly effects the learning environment of the students at tertiary level (Georges & Pallas, 2010). As the analysis of the research reported that boys were more confident than girls were impacted by their fear of failing academically due to communication gap (Goddard et al., 2017; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025a; Shoaib, Waris, et al., 2025a). Furthermore, the study findings indicate that girls access to high quality education is disproportionately greatly impacted by the gender disparity in lack of financial aid programs at university level (Goodman & Burton, 2012).

Culturally Relevant Teaching Materials:

The study findings summarized that students study material has been based on cultural codes. Similarly, the primary data analysis highlighted that student's cultural values has been practiced in classroom. Likewise, the study findings claimed that dress code of the students has been implemented. However, the summary of the frequency distribution declared that student's cultural values were very important in the classroom. Comparably, the statistical analysis confirmed that students gender based study culture has been practiced. Furthermore, the primary that analysis pointed out that students have freedom to practice cultural values. Correspondingly, the study findings asserted that students respects the teachers. In addition, the study findings indicated that student has respect in classroom in front of others. The study findings had been linked with the study findings as mentioned in review. The study findings outline that parents prefer more male for professional ambitions frequently take precedence over daughters for academic objectives, son preference significantly effects the learning outcomes of female (Gottfredson et al., 1995). In the same way, analysis of the study pointed out that students learning was significantly affected with overcrowded classroom environment at higher education level (Graham, 2023). However, the results of the study articulated that in male dominated classrooms system effects the girls were alienated by the absence of inclusive teaching strategies in educational institutions (Grineski, 2009). As the analysis of the research reported that girls were less exposed to a variety of skill development opportunities effects due to disparity in gendered extracurricular activities (Gullo & Ammar, 2022; Shoaib, Tariq, Rasool, et al., 2025; Shoaib & Ullah, 2025). Furthermore, the study findings indicate that disparity in regulation of rules, females significantly affected to encounter disproportionate consequences for violations of discipline in comparison to their male peers (Guterman & Neuman, 2019; Shoaib, Tariq, & Iqbal, 2025a, 2025b).

Conclusion

This study concludes that policy frameworks and institutional support are critical determinants in promoting equitable assessment and culturally relevant pedagogy in universities. Equitable assessment ensures that all students, regardless of their cultural, linguistic, or socio-economic backgrounds, have fair opportunities to demonstrate their learning, while culturally relevant pedagogy fosters engagement, inclusion, and a sense of belonging. The findings indicate that when institutional policies provide clear guidelines, resources, and professional development for faculty, the implementation of inclusive teaching and assessment practices is more consistent and effective. Conversely, gaps in policy enforcement or inadequate institutional support limit the adoption of these practices, perpetuating disparities in student learning experiences. Therefore, universities must strengthen policy frameworks and provide sustained institutional support to create inclusive learning environments that enhance academic success and foster equitable opportunities for all students.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, F., & Nisar, N. (2024). Women Academicians and Autonomy: Constructing Identities in Higher Education. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 2(4), 1053-1060. <https://ijssbulletin.com/index.php/IJSSB/article/view/161>
- Abdullah, F., & Ullah, H. (2016). Physical Violence on Women: A Comparative Study of Rural and Urban Areas of Muzaffarabad, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Gender and Social Issues*, 15(2), 113. <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A497793910/AONE?u=anon~54132f5b&sid=googleScholar&xid=c3282c17>
- Abdullah, F., & Ullah, H. (2022). Lived Experiences of Women Academicians in Higher Education Institutions of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *South Asian Studies*, 37(02), 323-340. <https://sasj.pu.edu.pk/9/article/view/1292>
- Abdullah, F., Matloob, T., & Malik, A. (2024). Decision-Making Trajectories of Working Women in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Policy Research Journal*, 2(4), 2189-2197.
- Abdullah, F., Nisar, N., & Ahmed, N. (2025). Career Trajectories of Women Academicians in Higher Education of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *The Knowledge*, 4(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.63062/tk/2k25b.42057>
- Abdullah, F., Nisar, N., Ahmed, N., & Sultana, R. (2025). Women's participation in educational development: From access to agency. *Research Consortium Archive*, 3(4), 625-634. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17534868>
- Abdullah, F., Shoukat, S., Malik, A., & Akhtar, S. (2025). Patriarchal Norms and Female Teachers' Participation in Decision-Making in Azad Jammu and Kashmir: *Pakistan Journal of Social Science Review*, 4(5), 1181-1191. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17491575>
- Abdullah, F., Sultana, R., & Nisar, N. (2025). Cultural reintegration and gendered expectations: The challenges of 'returning home'. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(7), 900-909. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948961>
- Abdullah, F., Sultana, R., & Nisar, N. (2025). Female Faculty Navigating Professional Journeys in Higher Education of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *ProScholar Insights*, 4(2), 179-187. <https://doi.org/10.55737/psi.2025b-42093>
- Abdullah, F., Sultana, R., Nisar, N., & Gorski, N. A. (2025). Women's Roles in Pastoral Societies: Responsibilities and Challenges. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(3), 388-395. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17645711>
- Abdullah, F., Ahmed, N., Shaheen, I., & Sultana, R. (2024). Women academicians' career progression in higher education of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Regional Lens*, 3(1), 86-94. <https://doi.org/10.62997/rl.2024.31042>

- Abdullah, F., Nisar, N., & Malik, A. (2024). Gendered higher education and women academicians' career development. *The Regional Tribune*, 3(1), 418-428. <https://doi.org/10.63062/trt/v24.076>
- Ahmed, R., Shoaib, M., & Zaman, M. A. (2025). Female Acceptability in STEM Higher Education in Pakistan: The Role of Gender Expression, Gender Sensitivity, and Supportiveness. *Annual Methodological Archive Research Review*, 3(7), 296-322.
- Ali, S. R., Shoaib, M., & Kausar, N. (2025). Gender Disparity in Enrolment, Classroom, Learning Environment, and Learning Achievements of the Students in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(3), 330-342.
- CohenMiller, A. S., Demers, D., Schnackenberg, H., & Izenkova, Z. (2022, 2022/01/02). "You Are Seen; You Matter:" Applying the Theory of Gendered Organizations to Equity and Inclusion for Motherscholars in Higher Education. *Journal of Women and Gender in Higher Education*, 15(1), 87-109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26379112.2022.2025816>
- Davies, I., Sekaram, S., Valerio, K., Parvez Butt, A., Kenny, L., & van Veen, S. (2024, 2024/08/17). Feminist and youth-led approaches to transforming social and gender norms in South and South-East Asia. *Development in Practice*, 34(6), 757-764. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2024.2379014>
- Flores, R. L. (2017, 2017/01/01). The rising gap between rich and poor: A look at the persistence of educational disparities in the United States and why we should worry. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 3(1), 1323698. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2017.1323698>
- Ford, M. (2013, 2013/01/01). Achievement gaps in Australia: what NAPLAN reveals about education inequality in Australia. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 16(1), 80-102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2011.645570>
- Gallagher, J. R., & Wahler, E. A. (2018, 2018/04/03). Racial Disparities in Drug Court Graduation Rates: The Role of Recovery Support Groups and Environments. *Journal of Social Work Practice in the Addictions*, 18(2), 113-127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533256X.2018.1448277>
- Garcia, D., Barnett, M. L., Rothenberg, W. A., Tonarely, N. A., Perez, C., Espinosa, N., Salem, H., Alonso, B., San Juan, J., Peskin, A., Davis, E. M., Davidson, B., Weinstein, A., Rivera, Y. M., Orbano-Flores, L. M., & Jent, J. F. (2023, 2023/05/04). A Natural Helper Intervention to Address Disparities in Parent Child-Interaction Therapy: A Randomized Pilot Study. *Journal of Clinical Child & Adolescent Psychology*, 52(3), 343-359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15374416.2022.2148255>
- Geduld, B. (2024, 2024/12/31). Parental involvement in homework to foster self-regulated learning skills: a qualitative study with parents from selected higher quintile schools. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2343526. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2343526>
- Gehlert, S., Murray, A., Sohmer, D., McClintock, M., Conzen, S., & Olopade, O. (2010, 2010/04/28). The Importance of Transdisciplinary Collaborations for Understanding and Resolving Health Disparities. *Social Work in Public Health*, 25(3-4), 408-422. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19371910903241124>
- Gentrup, S., & Rjosk, C. (2018, 2018/04/03). Pygmalion and the gender gap: do teacher expectations contribute to differences in achievement between boys and girls at the beginning of schooling? *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 24(3-5), 295-323. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803611.2018.1550840>

- Georges, A., & Pallas, A. M. (2010, 2010/04/15). New Look at a Persistent Problem: Inequality, Mathematics Achievement, and Teaching. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 103(4), 274-290. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220670903382996>
- Goddard, R. D., Skrla, L., & Salloum, S. J. (2017, 2017/10/02). The Role of Collective Efficacy in Closing Student Achievement Gaps: A Mixed Methods Study of School Leadership for Excellence and Equity. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk (JESPAR)*, 22(4), 220-236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10824669.2017.1348900>
- Goodman, R., & Burton, D. (2012, 2012/11/01). What is the nature of the achievement gap, why does it persist and are government goals sufficient to create social justice in the education system? *Education 3-13*, 40(5), 500-514. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2010.550586>
- Gottfredson, D. C., Marciniak, E. M., Birdseye, A. T., & Gottfredson, G. D. (1995, 1995/01/01). Increasing Teacher Expectations for Student Achievement. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 88(3), 155-163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.1995.9941294>
- Graham, M. A. (2023, 2023/05/04). Overcrowded Classrooms and their Association with South African Learners' Mathematics Achievement. *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 27(2), 169-179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18117295.2023.2244217>
- Grineski, S. E. (2009, 2009/05/01). Parental Accounts of Children's Asthma Care: The Role of Cultural and Social Capital in Health Disparities. *Sociological Focus*, 42(2), 107-132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00380237.2009.10571346>
- Gullo, D. F., & Ammar, A. A. (2022, 2022/08/18). Predicting third-grade academic achievement in low-socioeconomic children: developmental and socio-behavioural influences in kindergarten. *Early Child Development and Care*, 192(11), 1800-1815. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2021.1939694>
- Guterman, O., & Neuman, A. (2019, 2019/07/03). Similar goals, different results: differences in group learning goals and their impact on academic achievements. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 43(6), 729-741. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2017.1394990>
- Henderson, L., & Herring, C. (2013, 2013/09/01). Does critical diversity pay in higher education? Race, gender, and departmental rankings in research universities. *Politics, Groups, and Identities*, 1(3), 299-310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21565503.2013.818565>
- Herzig, P. (2010, 2010/09/01). Communal networks and gender: placing identities among South Asians in Kenya. *South Asian Diaspora*, 2(2), 165-184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19438192.2010.491296>
- Kamenou, N. (2020, 2020/05/26). Feminism in Cyprus: women's agency, gender, and peace in the shadow of nationalism. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 22(3), 359-381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2019.1687000>
- Rao, N., & Sweetman, C. (2014, 2014/01/02). Introduction to Gender and Education. *Gender & Development*, 22(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552074.2014.902230>
- Shoab, M. (2021). Sociological Analysis of Teachers Perspectives on Students Academic Performance in Higher Education in the Punjab [International Islamic University Islamabad]. Central Library.

- Shoaib, M. (2023a, September 22). Galvanising Bourdieu's typology with Pakistani education and social class. *The Nation*, 4.
- Shoaib, M. (2023b, December 05). Gender Differences in Academic Performance. *The Nation*.
- Shoaib, M. (2024a, January 09). Gender Disparity in Education. *The Nation*.
- Shoaib, M. (2024b). Gender Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(1), 207-222.
- Shoaib, M. (2024c, April 30). Gendered Space in Higher Education. *Daily Parliament Times*, 3.
- Shoaib, M. (2024d). Gendering Bourdieu's Cultural Capital in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(2), 265-278.
- Shoaib, M. (2024e). Tailoring Theoretical Lens and Nudging Bourdieu's Cultural Capital on Gender and Academic Performance. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 4(4), 87-101.
- Shoaib, M. (2025a). Academic Achievement and Gender Inequality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of Muslim Majority Nations. *Sociology & Cultural Research Review* 3(02), 373-380.
- Shoaib, M. (2025b). A Systematic Review of Gender Disparities in Academic Achievement in Higher Education Across Muslim Countries. *Advance Social Science Archive Journal*, 3(02), 1622-1639.
- Shoaib, M., & Bashir, Z. (2025, April 15). Virtual Classrooms and Academic Performance of the Students in Higher Education during the COVID-19 Outbreak 5th International Conference of PNQAHE and AGM on Stakeholder Engagement in Quality Assurance - Shaping Higher Education with Inputs from All Relevant Voices, Forman Christian College University, Lahore.
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2019). Female and Male Students' Educational Performance in Tertiary Education in the Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Issues*, X(1), 83-100.
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2021a). Classroom Environment, Teacher, and Girl Students' Learning Skills. *Education and Urban Society*, 53(9), 1039-1063. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00131245211001908>
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2021b). Teachers' perspectives on factors of female students' outperformance and male students' underperformance in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(3), 684-699. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-05-2020-0261>
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2025). Gender differentials in academic performance in Pakistani higher education*. *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 1-21.
- Shoaib, M., & Zaman, M. A. (2025). Evaluating Academic Performance in Higher Education during COVID-19 A Study of Virtual Learning Environments. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 4(4), 64-78.
- Shoaib, M., Abdullah, F., & Ali, N. (2021). A Research Visualization of Academic Learning Skills among Students in Higher Education Institutions: A Bibliometric Evidence from 1981 to 2020. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 5579, 1-34.
- Shoaib, M., Ahmed, R., & Iqbal, S. (2025). Female Acceptability in Stem Higher Education in Pakistan: The Interplay of Careerist Femininity, Job Oriented, and Family Orientation. *Journal for Current Sign*, 3(3), 181-202.
- Shoaib, M., Ahmed, R., & Usmani, F. (2025a). Empirical Study on Acceptability and Resistance to Feminization in STEM Fields at the Higher Education Level. *Physical Education, Health and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 135-143.
- Shoaib, M., Ahmed, R., & Usmani, F. (2025b). Feminization in STEM Fields in Higher Education in Pakistan: A Case of Female Acceptability and Resistance. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(3), 646-660.

- Shoaib, M., Ahmed, R., Iqbal, S., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Feminization of STEM Education in Higher Education: Arrays of Acceptability and Resistance. *Research Consortium Archive*, 3(2), 1002-1021.
- Shoaib, M., Ahmed, R., Zaman, M. A., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Exploring Acceptability and Resistance to Feminization in STEM Fields: An Empirical Perspective from Higher Education. *Dialogue Social Science Review (DSSR)*, 3(7), 722-736.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, N., Anwar, B., Rasool, S., Mustafa, R.-e., & Zici, S. (2021). Research Visualization on Teaching, Language, Learning of English and Higher Education Institutions from 2011 to 2020: A Bibliometric Evidences Library Philosophy and Practice, 5677, 1-27.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, S. R., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Self-Fulfilling Prophecy of Learning Skills Among Students in Higher Education. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(7), 164-177.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, S. R., & Kausar, N. (2025). Gender Disparity on Teaching Materials, Communication, Institutional Support, and Learning Achievements of the Students in Higher Education in Pakistan. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(7), 169-183.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, S. R., Iqbal, T., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Gender Disparity in Learning Achievements of the Students in Higher Education in Pakistan. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(6), 840-853.
- Shoaib, M., Batool, F., Kausar, N., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Research on Learning Modalities A Bibliometric Study of Global Scholarship (2001-2023). *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(8), 1083-1101.
- Shoaib, M., Iqbal, A., & Iftikhar, I. (2025). Engagement of Students in Learning in Higher Education: The Role of Academic Library Spaces. *The Regional Tribune*, 4(3), 311-328.
- Shoaib, M., Iqbal, S., Rasool, S., & Abdullah, F. (2025). A Sociological Perspective on Gender Disparities in Higher Education in Pakistan. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(10), 560-572.
- Shoaib, M., Kausar, N., Ali, S. R., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Gender Disparity in Learning Achievements in Higher Education: Insights from a Literature Review. *Policy Research Journal*, 3(6), 634-648.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., & Iqbal, S. (2025a). Gendered Reflections on Third Space Pedagogy and Classroom Practices in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Physical Education, Health and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 374-385.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., & Iqbal, S. (2025b). Sociological Perspectives on Inclusive Pedagogy in Higher Education Classrooms in Pakistan. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(4), 1845-1854.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., & Iqbal, S. (2025c). Trends and Paradoxes of Gender in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 4(9), 37-51.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., & Zaman, M. A. (2025a). Feminist Pedagogies and Gender Sensitive Teaching Practices in Pakistani Higher Education. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(4), 179-190.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., & Zaman, M. A. (2025b). Feminist Praxis and Pedagogical Approaches in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 4(8), 145-160.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., & Zaman, M. A. (2025c). Gender and Cultural dynamics in Shaping Pedagogical Practices in Pakistani Higher Education. *Physical Education, Health and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 105-118.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., Iqbal, S., & Abdullah, F. (2025a). Empowerment of Females Through Knowledge in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(5), 636-648.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., Iqbal, S., & Abdullah, F. (2025b). A Sociological Analysis of Gender and Digital Pedagogy in Higher Education: Perspectives from Pakistani Context. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(5), 968-981.

- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., Kalsoom, A., & Ali, S. R. (2025). Exploring Gender-Based Dissimilarities in Educational Outcomes at the Tertiary Level: A Review of Existing Literature. *Policy Research Journal*, 3(7), 287-302.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., Zaman, M. A., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Gendered Pathways and Global Knowledge Flows in the Transformation of Pakistani Higher Education. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(10), 308-322.
- Shoaib, M., Rasool, S., Zaman, M. A., & Ahmed, R. (2025). An Empirical Insight into Acceptability and Resistance to Feminization in STEM Fields at the Higher Education Level. *Research Consortium Archive*, 3(3), 157-178.
- Shoaib, M., Shamsher, A., & Iqbal, S. (2025). A Systematic Review of Academic Library Spaces as Facilitators of Student Engagement in Higher Education Learning. *The Knowledge*, 4(1), 123-134.
- Shoaib, M., Shamsher, A., & Iqbal, S. (2025). Understanding Student Engagement in Higher Education: The Contribution of Academic Library Spaces. *ProScholar Insights*, 4(1), 245-257.
- Shoaib, M., Shehzadi, K., & Abbas, Z. (2024a). Inclusivity and Teachers' Aptitude in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(6), 219-237.
- Shoaib, M., Shehzadi, K., & Abbas, Z. (2024b). Inclusivity, Teacher Competency, and Learning Environment at Higher Education: Empirical Evidences. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(5), 244-261.
- Shoaib, M., Tariq, I., & Iqbal, S. (2025a). Extracurricular Activities in Higher Education: Diversity and Inclusion. *Regional Lens*, 4(1), 174-187.
- Shoaib, M., Tariq, I., & Iqbal, S. (2025b). Intersectionality and Student Inclusion in Higher Education: A Study of Class, Residence, Culture, and Extracurricular Participation. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(1), 1-14.
- Shoaib, M., Tariq, I., Rasool, S., & Iqbal, S. (2025). The Role of Extracurricular Activities in Fostering Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education: A Systematic Review. *Advance Social Science Archive Journal*, 3(2), 1377-1392.
- Shoaib, M., Waris, T., & Iqbal, S. (2025a). A Review-Based Examination of Gender Dynamics in Virtual Learning Environments in Higher Education. *Sociology & Cultural Research Review*, 3(02), 448-454.
- Shoaib, M., Waris, T., & Iqbal, S. (2025a). Assessing Gendered Participation Spaces in Online Learning Environments in Higher Education in Pakistan. *The Knowledge*, 4(2), 63-74.
- Shoaib, M., Waris, T., & Iqbal, S. (2025b). Gender Dynamics in Online Higher Education: Insights from Empirical Evidence. *The Regional Tribune*, 4(2), 89-102.
- Shoaib, M., Waris, T., & Iqbal, S. (2025b). Virtual Learning Environments and Gendered Spaces in Higher Education in Pakistan: A Quantitative Approach. *Regional Lens*, 4(2), 65-78.
- Shoaib, M., Waris, T., & Iqbal, S. (2025c). A Quantitative Study of Gendered Interactions and Spatial Perceptions in Online Higher Education in Pakistan. *ProScholar Insights*, 4(2), 96-108.
- Shoaib, M., Zaman, M. A., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Trends of Research Visualization of Gender Based Violence (GBV) from 1971-2020: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(7), 203-216.
- Shoaib, M., Zaman, M. A., & Abdullah, F. (2025). Gender and Health through a Feminist Lens: Sociological Insights from Pakistan. *Research Consortium Archive*, 3(4), 1075-1086.